

Materials for the paper “A Robust LSTM-based Test Selection Method for Self-Driving Cars”

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Appendix A - Performance of SDC-Scissor

The performance measures for SDC-Scissor when using Dataset-1¹, Dataset-2, Dataset-1-30, and Dataset-1-10, are presented in Tables 1 and 2. For each performance metric, the best values are shown in italics. One can see that no model is the best in all performance metrics no matter what dataset is used.

Table 1: SDC-Scissor Setup-1 and Setup-2 performance

Setup-1				
Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Random Forest	0.62	0.65	0.81	0.72
Gradient Boosting	<i>0.63</i>	0.64	<i>0.88</i>	<i>0.74</i>
Support Vector Machine	<i>0.63</i>	0.65	0.86	<i>0.74</i>
Gaussian Naive Bayes	0.57	<i>0.67</i>	0.60	0.63
Logistic Regression	<i>0.63</i>	0.65	0.85	<i>0.74</i>
Decision Tree	0.56	0.65	0.63	0.64
Average Values	0.61	0.65	0.77	0.70
Setup-2				
Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Random Forest	0.62	<i>0.65</i>	0.83	0.73
Gradient Boosting	0.61	0.64	0.88	0.74
Support Vector Machine	<i>0.63</i>	0.64	<i>0.91</i>	<i>0.75</i>
Gaussian Naive Bayes	0.59	<i>0.65</i>	0.74	0.69
Logistic Regression	<i>0.63</i>	0.64	0.90	<i>0.75</i>
Decision Tree	0.56	<i>0.65</i>	0.63	0.64
Average Values	0.61	0.65	0.82	0.72

¹ Dataset-1 is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14599223> The dataset contains 10000 test cases. A test case contains [(x,y), (x,y), ..., (x,y)] road coordinates as a list and interpolated road coordinates to create texture as an asphalt plane in the simulator. BeamNG.tech v24 is used as a simulation environment to label data.

Table 2: SDC-Scissor Setup-5 and Setup-6 performance

Setup-5				
Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Random Forest	0.62	0.66	0.80	0.72
Gradient Boosting	<i>0.63</i>	0.66	<i>0.85</i>	<i>0.74</i>
Support Vector Machine	<i>0.63</i>	0.66	<i>0.85</i>	<i>0.74</i>
Gaussian Naive Bayes	0.59	<i>0.67</i>	0.65	0.66
Logistic Regression	<i>0.63</i>	0.66	0.84	<i>0.74</i>
Decision Tree	0.57	0.65	0.65	0.65
Average Values	0.61	0.66	0.77	0.71
Setup-6				
Random Forest	<i>0.74</i>	<i>0.79</i>	0.80	0.79
Gradient Boosting	0.73	0.78	0.78	0.78
Support Vector Machine	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.79
Gaussian Naive Bayes	0.67	0.74	0.72	0.73
Logistic Regression	<i>0.74</i>	0.77	<i>0.84</i>	<i>0.80</i>
Decision Tree	0.67	0.74	0.71	0.72
Average Values	0.71	0.77	0.78	0.77

Appendix B - Average training and validation loss of ITS4SDC models across four setups

Typically, explanations for varying performance are based on a discussion of dataset size, data quality, and potential overfitting. The latter can be excluded for ITS4SDC due to the early stopping mechanism used in model training (see also Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4). Dataset sizes vary strongly between Dataset-1, Dataset-1-30, Dataset-2, and Dataset-1-10, i.e., from 10,000 over 4,746 and 3,559 down to 1,324, respectively. The quality of Dataset-1 is good. It contains a wide range of different test roads and the labels are correct. The quality of Dataset-2 is equally good regarding test road variance, but probing into the correctness of labels assigned indicated the presence of noise. The manual analysis of a randomly picked sample of 200 test roads from Dataset-2 showed that more than 20% were labeled incorrectly. It is unclear how the noise got into Dataset-2. A possible explanation could be that labels were assigned using a version of the BeamNG.tech simulator different to the one used in this study.

Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4 show the validation loss during the training phase of the models. Since cross-fold validation was applied, the mean values for each fold were calculated for the corresponding epoch. When early stopping was triggered for a fold, the best model, determined by the lowest validation loss, was saved. In each figure, the red vertical line indicates the epoch at which early stopping was triggered for one of the folds. The earliest and latest triggered early stopping points, as well as the early stopping point of the fold that achieved the lowest validation loss, are marked with vertical lines. Where multiple folds have the

same epoch number at which early stopping was triggered, fewer early stopping vertical lines may be observed than the selected number of k-folds, as seen in Figures 2, 3 and 4. In Figure 1, the separation of validation loss and training loss demonstrates potential overfitting when early stopping is not applied.

Fig. 1: Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-1 (ITS4SDC).

Appendix C - Confusion matrices of ITS4SDC models across six setups

To further analyze the ITS4SDC’s classification performance, confusion matrices are presented in Figure 5. The confusion matrices for Setups 1, 2, 5, and 6 have been calculated by averaging the k-folds. These matrices help analyze how well the model distinguishes between PASS and FAIL cases. A high number of false positives (FP) indicates overestimating road safety, while a high number of false negatives (FN) suggests the model is overly conservative in labeling roads as unsafe. If FN increases, the probability of the selected tests passing increases, leading to the execution of unnecessary tests. This results in a higher time cost spent on testing. On the other hand, if FP increases, more failing tests are misclassified as passing, causing the test suite to contain easier roads rather than the more challenging ones where the SDC is expected to fail.

Fig. 2: Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-2 (ITS4SDC).

Fig. 3: Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-5 (ITS4SDC).

Fig. 4: Mean training and validation loss across all folds for Setup-6 (ITS4SDC).

Fig. 5: Confusion matrices across setups